

Glutathione (deproteinization) Assay Kit

(Colorimetric Method)

Serial No: A006

Pack: 100T/96S

Nanjing Jiancheng Bioengineering Institute

CATALOGUE

1. Introduction.....	1
2. Reagent Composition & Preparation.....	1
3. Required Equipments & Reagents.....	2
4. Operation Procedures.....	3
5. Announcements.....	4
6. About Company.....	5
Appendix I: Whole blood GSH Assay.....	6
Appendix II: Blood Serum (or Plasma) GSH Assay..	8
Appendix III: Tissue GSH Assay.....	10

1. INTRODUCTION

This kit can be used for laboratory research only.

(1) Assay significance:

Glutathione (GSH) is a low molecular mundificant which can get rid of O_2^- , H_2O_2 & LOOH. GSH is a tripeptide composed by glutamic acid, glycine & cysteine, it is main non-protein sulfhydryl compound in tissue and substrate of GSH-PX & GST (GSH-PX & GST need GSH to decompose hydroperoxides). GSH can also stabilize sulfhydryl containing enzymes and avoid oxidative damage of hemoglobin & other cofactors. Recently, GSH is proved to participate function of recovering vitamin E to reduction form. Absence or exhausting of GSH will induct various chemicals or environmental factors to cause or aggratate toxication, it may relate to increasing oxidative damage, so GSH content is an important factor to measure oxidizing ability in vivo.

(2) Assay principle:

Dithio-dinitrobenzoic acid can react with sulfhydryl compounds to produce a yellow compound, it can be quantitative estimated by colorimetric method.

2. REAGENT COMPOSITION & PREPARATION

Reagent 1: Powder A×1 bottle, Solution B ×1 bottle, can be stored at 2-8℃ for 6 months.

Solution A preparation: Add 170ml 90~100℃ hot distilled water, dissolve completely.

Reagent 1 working solution: Mix Solution A with Solution B sufficiently. This working solution is supersaturated, if there are crystals seed out after cooling at room temperature, then please take supernatant for experiments. It can be stored for 6 months.

Reagent 2: Powder×1 bottle, when use, please add double distilled water until volume reaches 200ml, dissolve sufficiently. It can be stored in plastic bottle (gift from our Institute) for 6 months.

Reagent 3: Powder × 1 vial, when use, please add double distilled water until volume reaches 50ml, dissolve sufficiently. It can be stored at 2-8°C away from light for 6 months.

Reagent 4: Powder × 4 vials, when use, please add 10ml distilled water in each vial to dissolve, can be cold stored away from light for 5 days.

Reagent 5: GSH standard powder 3.07mg × 3 vials, can be stored at 2-8°C for 6 months.

Reagent 6: GSH standard solvent stock solution 10ml × 1 bottle, can be cold stored in fridge for 6 months.

GSH standard solvent working solution preparation: Dilute stock solution with double distilled water at ratio of 1:9 in order to prepare GSH standard solvent working solution, please control solution volume according to you need. Working solution should be used soon after preparation.

1mmol/L GSH standard solution: GSH's molecular weight is 307. Add 3.07mg GSH standard powder in 10ml GSH standard solvent working solution, mix sufficiently, please use this solution soon after preparation.

20 μ mol/L GSH standard solution: Dilute 0.2ml 1mmol/L GSH standard solution with 9.8ml GSH standard solvent working solution, mix sufficiently, please use this solution soon after preparation.

3. REQUIRED EQUIPMENTS & REAGENTS

- An spectrophotometer (such as 721, 722) capable of measuring absorbance at 420nm
- Desk centrifuge
- Micropipets and tips
- Vortex mixer
- A source of pure water (preferably double distilled water and double distilled water)

4. OPERATION PROCEDURE

(1) Supernatant preparation:

Take 0.5ml sample to assay, add 2ml Reagent 1 working solution, mix sufficiently, centrifugate at 3500~4000rpm for 10 minutes. Take 1ml supernatant for colorable reaction.

(2) Colorable reaction:

	Blank tube	Standard tube	Sample tube
Reagent 1 (ml)	1.0		
20 μ mol/LGSH standard (ml)		1.0	
Supernatant (ml)			1.0
Reagent 2 (ml)	1.25	1.25	1.25
Reagent 3 (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25
Reagent 4 (ml)	0.05	0.05	0.05
Mix sufficiently, place quescently for 5 minutes, transfer in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 420nm (adjust zero by distilled water).			

(3) Calculation:

① By formula (according to standard concentration):

$$\text{GSH content (gGSH/L)} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}} \times \text{Standard concentration (20}\mu\text{mol/L)} \times \frac{\text{GSH molecular weight (307)}}{\text{Dilution times}}$$

② By standard curve:

Standard curve preparation: Take 0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0ml 1mmol/L GSH standard solution, transfer them in 10ml volumetric flask separately, add SSH standard solvent working solution until volumes reach to 10ml, a series of 0, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 μ mol/L GSH standard solution is prepared. Operate according to operation table, transfer solutions in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 420nm (adjust zero by blank tube). Use concentration as x-axis, use OD value as y-axis, draw standard curve. Check corresponding concentration of OD_{Sample} on standard curve.

5. ANNOUNCEMENTS

- (1) Erythrocytes contain majority of GSH in blood, so GSH content can express in gGSH/L whole blood or in GSH content per gram Hb.
- (2) Extinction coefficient is used in calculation, so spectrophotometer should be adjusted wavelength. It's better to calculate according to standard concentration because its convenience & accuracy.
- (3) It is better to use 5ml dropper with scales or micropipet, please avoid suck the membrane at surface, insert in supernant, take 2ml for colorable reaction.
- (4) It is suggested to make 2 standard tubes & 2 blank tubes for each batch in order to reduce procedural errors

6. ABOUT COMPANY

<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Nanjing Jiancheng Bioengineering Institute</u> <u>Nanjing Jiancheng Technology Co.Ltd.</u></p>			
Address:	Room 1106, Floor 11, New Li-Ji Mansion, No.258-27, Zhongyang Road, Nanjing	Telephone:	(025) 83360321 83360969 83113890
Postcode:	210009		83112287(finances) 83360272(technology)
Contact person:	Jianping Ji	Fax:	(025) 83227943 83609960
Complaint phone:	(025) 57713719/13813881385	Message:	13815858329
Homepage:	www.njcbio.com (Jiancheng biology) www.njctech.com (Jiancheng technology)	E-mail:	njcbio@vip.163.com answer@njcbio.com

APPENDIX I: WHOLE BLOOD GSH ASSAY

1. Sample pretreatment:

1:9 hemolysate preparation: Take 0.1ml heparin anticoagulated whole blood, add 0.9ml double distilled water, mix sufficiently until hemolysate becomes limpid.

2. Operation procedure:

(1) Supernatant preparation: Take 0.5ml 1:9 hemolysate, add 2ml Reagent 1 working solution, mix sufficiently, centrifugate at 3500~4000rpm for 10 minutes. Take 1ml supernatant for colorable reaction.

(2) Colorable reaction:

	Blank tube	Standard tube	Sample tube
Reagent 1 (ml)	1.0		
20 μ mol/LGSH standard (ml)		1.0	
Supernatant (ml)			1.0
Reagent 2 (ml)	1.25	1.25	1.25
Reagent 3 (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25
Reagent 4 (ml)	0.05	0.05	0.05
Mix sufficiently, place quescently for 5 minutes, transfer in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 420nm (adjust zero by distilled water).			

3. Calculation:

① Formula:

$$\text{Whole blood GSH content (gGSH/L)} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}} \times \text{Standard concentration (20}\mu\text{mol/L)} \times \frac{\text{GSH molecular weight (307)}}{+10^6} \times \text{Dilution times}$$

Note: Dilution times= Hemolysate preparation dilution times × Supernatant preparation dilution times=10 × 5

$$\text{Whole blood GSH content (gGSH/L)} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}} \times \text{Standard concentration (20}\mu\text{mol/L)} \times \frac{\text{GSH molecular weight (307)}}{+10^6} \times \text{Dilution times} + 10^6 \times \frac{\text{Hemoglobin content in whole blood (gHb/L)}}{+10^6}$$

② Example:

Take 0.1ml anticoagulated human whole blood to measure GSH content, in results, $\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}}$ is 0.149, $\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}}$ is 0.116, OD_{Blank} is 0.011, hemoglobin content in whole blood is 132Hb/L. Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Whole blood GSH content (gGSH/L)} &= \frac{0.149 - 0.011}{0.116 - 0.011} \times 20 \times 307 \times 10 \times 5 \div 10^6 \\ &= 0.403 \text{gGSH / L} \\ &\text{(1 liter whole blood contains 0.403g GSH)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Whole blood GSH content (gGSH/gHb)} &= \frac{0.149 - 0.011}{0.116 - 0.011} \times 20 \times 307 \times 10 \times 5 \div 10^6 \div 132 \\ &= 3.057 \text{mgGSH / gHb} \\ &\text{(1 g hemoglobin contains 3.057 mg GSH)} \end{aligned}$$

APPENDIX II: BLOOD SERUM (OR PLASMA) GSH ASSAY

1. Sample pretreatment:

Take blood serum (or plasma) to assay directly.

2. Operation procedure:

(1) **Supernatant preparation:** Take 0.5ml blood serum (or plasma), add 2ml Reagent 1 working solution, mix sufficiently, centrifugate at 3500~4000rpm for 10 minutes. Take 1ml supernatant for colorable reaction.

(2) Colorable reaction:

	Blank tube	Standard tube	Sample tube
Reagent 1 (ml)	1.0		
20 μ mol/LGSH standard (ml)		1.0	
Supernatant (ml)			1.0
Reagent 2 (ml)	1.25	1.25	1.25
Reagent 3 (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25
Reagent 4 (ml)	0.05	0.05	0.05

Mix sufficiently, place quiescently for 5 minutes, transfer in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 420nm (adjust zero by distilled water).

3. Calculation:

① Formula:

$$\text{Blood serum (or plasma) GSH content (mgGSH/L)} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}} \times \text{Standard concentration (20}\mu\text{mol/L)} \times \frac{\text{GSH molecular weight (307)}}{10^3} \times \text{Sample dilution times before assay}$$

Note: Dilution times= Supernatant preparation dilution times (5)

② Example:

Take 0.5ml anticoagulated human blood plasma to measure GSH content, in results, $\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}}$ is 0.027, $\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}}$ is 0.117, OD_{Blank} is 0.016. Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Blood plasma GSH content (mgGSH/L)} &= \frac{0.027 - 0.016}{0.117 - 0.016} \times 20 \times 307 \times 5 \div 10^3 \\ &= 3.343 \text{ mgGSH / L} \end{aligned}$$

APPENDIX III: TISSUE GSH ASSAY

1. Sample pretreatment:

Tissue homogenate should according to Experimental Methodology.

2. Operation procedure:

(1) Supernatant preparation: Take 0.5ml 10% homogenate supernatant, add 2ml Reagent 1 working solution, mix sufficiently, centrifugate at 3500~4000rpm for 10 minutes. Take 1ml supernatant for colorable reaction.

(2) Colorable reaction:

	Blank tube	Standard tube	Sample tube
Reagent 1 (ml)	1.0		
20 μ mol/LGSH standard (ml)		1.0	
Supernatant (ml)			1.0
Reagent 2 (ml)	1.25	1.25	1.25
Reagent 3 (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25
Reagent 4 (ml)	0.05	0.05	0.05
Mix sufficiently, place quescently for 5 minutes, transfer in cuvettes of 1cm light path, measure OD values of all tubes at 420nm (adjust zero by distilled water).			

3. Calculation:

① Formula:

$$\text{Tissue GSH content (mgGSH/gprot)} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Blank}}} \times \frac{\text{Standard concentration (20}\mu\text{mol/L)}}{\text{GSH molecular weight (307)}} \times \text{GSH molecular weight (307)} \times \text{Dilution times} + 10^3 + \text{Protein concentration in sample to assay}$$

Note: Dilution times= Supernatant preparation dilution times (5)

② Example:

Take 0.5ml 10% mouse liver homogenate to measure GSH content, in results, $\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}}$ is 0.123, $\text{OD}_{\text{Standard}}$ is 0.117, OD_{Blank} is 0.016. protein concentration in 10% mouse liver homogenate is 11.257gprot/L. Calculate as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tissue GSH content (mgGSH/gprot)} &= \frac{0.123 - 0.016}{0.117 - 0.016} \times 20 \times 307 \times 5 + 10^3 + 11.257 \\ &= 2.889 \text{mgGSH / gprot} \end{aligned}$$